

GROWTH OF E-VEHICLE AND DE-GROWTH OF AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Abstract

The Indian automobile industry became the 4th largest in the world with sales increasing 9.5 per cent year-on-year to 4.02 million units in 2017. It was the 7th largest manufacturer of commercial vehicles in 2018. The two wheelers segment dominates the market in terms of volume owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector. India is also a prominent auto exporter and has strong export growth expectations for the near future. Automobile exports grew 14.5 per cent during FY 2019. But in recent days the industry faced negative growth due to various reasons. The automobile sector is one of the largest employers in the country, employing about 37 million people, directly and indirectly. The Indian automobile industry is one of the largest growing markets of the world, and contributes highly in the country's manufacturing facilities. Not only this, the automotive industry in India is further expected to pull up the share of manufacturing in India's GDP to 25 per cent by 2022 from 15 per cent currently, with production of electric vehicles being new talk of the town. However, India's electric vehicle industry is a newly born baby when compared with the other international markets such as US, China, Europe, etc. But, a face change is definitely anticipated for India's EV industry with major thrust given by the government. This article discuss the reason for de-growth of Indian automobile industry and growth of e-vehicle in Indian and international markets.

Key words: Automobile industry, electric vehicles, original equipment manufacturer, environmental friendly vehicles, etc.

1. Introduction

The automobile industry faced negative growth during the financial year 2019-20. The current slowdown in the Indian automobile sector is very different from the ones that the industry has gone through earlier. First, the slowdown is driven by domestic factors, including the non-banking financial companies crisis, while the earlier ones were triggered by global events. It also pointed out that over

FY 19-21; vehicle prices are estimated to jump 13-30 per cent due to safety, insurance and emission-related compliance costs. For end consumers, such a steep price hike can prove a hurdle in growth recovery. Meanwhile, growing competition from the pre-owned cars market is also pulling down sales of new vehicles. For example, in the passenger vehicles segment, while the new vehicles market grew 2 per cent in FY19 and the pre-owned market saw double-digit growth. The auto industry has been unable to arrest plunging sales in spite of new launches and offers and has been demanding immediate government intervention. Pointing out that the industry's turnover is close to half of the manufacturing GDP, accounting for about 11 per cent of the entire GST revenues of the country, the auto sector is hoping that the government will come out with a revival package ahead of the festive season to yield benefits. The industry's demands include a reduction in GST to 18 per cent from the current rate of 28 per cent, which will help in an immediate price reduction.

2. Objectives of the study

1. To know the current status of the automobile industry in India.
2. To know the trend in e-vehicle in India and rest of the world.
3. To know the India's plan to increase the sale of e-vehicles.

3. Collection of data

The present study is mainly based on secondary data which were collected from the facts and figures published by Automobile Manufacturers Association of India. Further, the data were collected from time to time from the Government of India websites. Further it was supplemented by the other sources like Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers, information is also tapped from journals, magazines, related websites and daily newspapers. The study is mainly based on secondary data. The external source includes internet, published data printed and electronic that is newspapers, journals, annual reports, books, etc.

4. Recent trends in Indian automobile industry - Production

The Indian automobile industry produced a total 12,020,944 vehicles including passenger vehicles, commercial vehicles, three wheelers, two wheelers and quadric cycle in April-August 2019 as against 13,699,848 in April-August 2018, registering a de-growth (-) 12.25 per cent over the same period last year.

5. Domestic sales

The sale of passenger vehicles declined by (-) 23.54 per cent in April-August 2019 over the same period last year. Within the passenger vehicles, the sales for passenger cars, utility vehicle & vans declined by (-) 29.41 per cent, (-) 6.27 per cent and (-) 34.04 per cent respectively in April-August 2019 over the same period last year. The overall commercial vehicles segment registered a decline of (-) 19.00 per cent in April-August 2019 as compared to the same period last year. Medium & heavy commercial vehicles declined by (-) 28.98 per cent and light commercial vehicles declined by (-) 12.70 per cent in April-August 2019 over the same period last year.

Figure 1: Domestic Sale during April-August 2019

Three wheelers sales declined by (-) 7.32 per cent in April-August 2019 over the same period last year. Within the three wheelers, passenger carrier sales

registered de-growth of (-) 7.25 per cent and goods carrier declined by (-) 7.64 per cent in April-August 2019 over April-August 2018. Two wheelers sales registered de-growth of (-) 14.85 per cent in April-August 2019 over April-August 2018. Within the two wheelers segment, scooters, motorcycles and mopeds declined by (-) 17.01 per cent, (-) 13.42 per cent and (-) 20.39 per cent respectively in April-August 2019 over April-August 2018.

6. Exports

In April-August 2019, overall automobile exports grew by 1.42 per cent where passenger vehicles and two wheelers exports grew by 4.13 per cent and 4.52 per cent respectively. However, commercial vehicles and three wheelers registered de-growth of (-) 44.44 per cent, and (-) 12.40 per cent respectively in April-August 2019 over the same period last year. Like any transformative new technology, electric vehicles create a variety of potent economic development challenges and opportunities. While the electric vehicle market is still at a relatively early stage of development, it is poised to reshape industries and communities the world over.

7. Global electric vehicle market

In 2018, the global EV sales, which include BEVs, PHEVs, and FCEVs, crossed 2 million units to reach a final figure of 2,218,490 units. The increasing popularity of EVs highlights significant efforts made jointly by various governments and automotive industry associations. However, more than 70 per cent of EV sales worldwide in 2018 were in the US, Japan, and China. Increasing pollution and threat of global warming have accentuated the need to replace petroleum-fueled vehicles with emission-free substitutes. After decades of R&D, the industry has found EVs to be the best suitable substitute for traditionally fueled vehicles, which has resulted in the emergence of electric vehicles. EV promotion efforts are increasing with continuous support from many governments, automotive OEMs, and other government & non-government agencies that are not only promoting the sales of zero-emission vehicles but also taking steps toward a

favorable regulatory framework, charging infrastructure, and financial support. Ambitious EV targets and policy support from governments have resulted in lowering of EV costs. In addition, factors such as extended vehicle range and improvement in charging infrastructure have fueled the demand for EVs globally. Led by China, Asia Pacific has the highest sales of EVs. China is focusing on EVs to deal with rising vehicle emissions in the country. The Chinese government provides subsidies for the electrification of vehicles, which, in turn, have increased the sales of EVs in China. The subsidies are offered for both pure EVs and HEVs. For instance, the government subsidy includes passenger car purchasing incentives. Over the years, the cost of batteries has reduced, which would again have a positive impact on the Chinese EV market. The Electric Vehicles Initiative (EVI), a multi-government policy forum dedicated to accelerating the introduction and adoption of electric vehicles worldwide has set a target of reaching an electric car fleet of 20 million by 2020, globally. The Paris Declaration on Electro Mobility and Climate Change has also set a similar global deployment target of 100 million electric cars by 2030. The growth of the EV market is driven by government funding, subsidies, and incentives, growing demand for EVs, increasing concerns over environmental pollution, and huge investments from automakers in EVs. However, factors such as high cost, smaller distance covered by EVs, and lack of standardization can restrain the market growth. BYD Auto Co., Ltd. (China), Nissan Motor Company Ltd. (Japan), Tesla Motors (US), and Volkswagen (Germany) are some of the leading players in the EV market. These companies have launched EVs in different segments to cater to the increased demand. Tesla Model S, Nissan Leaf, and BYD Tang are some of the most successful models that have attracted customers toward EVs. Panasonic Corporation (Japan), Automotive Energy Supply Corporation (Japan), BYD Auto Co., Ltd. (China), and Samsung SDI (South Korea) are some of the largest battery manufacturers that cater to the global demand for EV batteries.

8. Electric car market

This vehicle segment is the most promising market for EVs as it is the

largest segment in the automotive industry. The passenger car segment of the EV market is growing at a significant rate in emerging economies of the Asia Pacific region. The market growth in the region can be attributed to a rise in the GDP and population, improvement in lifestyle, increased purchasing power of consumers, and development of infrastructure. Passenger cars account for the largest share of the EV market. The demand for passenger cars has increased due to increase in demand for EVs. Countries such as China have a low waiting period for EVs as compared to ICE vehicles. Due to the growing stringency in emission norms, European countries such as Germany plan to have one million EVs on the road by 2020. China dominates the market for passenger electric cars, followed by the US.

9. Developments toward e-vehicles in India

Currently, EVs constitute less than 1 per cent of all the vehicles sold in India. There are more than 400,000 units of electric two-wheelers and only a few thousand electric cars on Indian roads. According to the Society of Manufacturers of Electric Vehicles, more than 95% of electric vehicles in India are low-speed electric scooters (25 km/h), which do not require registration and licenses. The manufacturers are waiting for the government to clear regulatory hurdles and come up with a clear stance on infrastructure development for EVs. In December 2017, the government announced an investment of USD 64.1 million in its FAME initiative for launching electric buses, taxis, and three-wheelers in 11 Indian cities. This initiative will boost the rate of EV adoption in India in the coming years. Moreover, in January 2019, under the FAME II mission, the Indian government allocated INR 350 crore for investments in research and innovation of 3 major components. Transportation ministry and authorities in India, proactively increase incentive-based mandates for EVs in the country by relevant stakeholders (automotive OEMs, Tier 1 players, and technology solution providers), similar to the emission norms mandates. This would build confidence in automotive OEMs and Tier 1 players in the country to invest appropriately in the required infrastructure and technology for these vehicles. In India, no OEM is ready to make huge investments in EVs like Tesla does in the US. A Tesla-like ecosystem

needs to be created in India by Indian manufacturers. The government needs to entertain OEMs and component manufactures to create an ecosystem to make products for India. The government should provide subsidies for OEMs to create extensive charging infrastructure across India. This will encourage more consumers to buy an EV. The government should also create alternate ways to generate electricity for fueling EVs since electricity for vehicles is only as clean as the fuel that was used to produce it. The US produces 66 per cent of the electricity from fossil fuel, Germany 50 per cent, and India almost 60 per cent. We cannot use thermal or fossil fuel to produce electricity to power EVs. It can cause more damage to the environment. Electricity for EVs should be generated using renewable sources like bio gas, solar power, etc. The government should take initiatives for creating more renewable energy sources across the country. In India, R&D of EVs is quite low because of fewer resources with knowledge on EV concepts. Governments of various states in India should create courses on EVs in colleges. These resources can be used for R&D in manufacturing units, which will boost the EV R&D in India.

10. Current scenario of EV sales and incentives in India

In FY2019, The total EV sales reached a total of 759,600 units, which includes electric two-wheelers (126,000), electric three-wheelers (630,000), and electric passenger vehicles (3,600). The electric two-wheeler market witnessed a growth of 130 per cent (YoY). The growth is due to the government announcement of the FAME-II (Faster Adoption and Manufacturing of Electric Vehicles) policy.

FAME-I: It is an incentive scheme for the promotion of electric and hybrid vehicles in India. The objective of the scheme is to promote electric mobility. It also provides financial incentives for attractive EV production and creation of electric transportation infrastructure. FAME-I started in 2015 and was completed in March 2019.

FAME-II: The Indian government rolled out FAME-II scheme for clean mobility. Under this scheme, 100,000 registered electric two-wheelers with a maximum ex-factory price will be eligible to avail incentive of INR 20,000 each. The scheme is proposed to get implemented over a period of 3 years effective from April 1, 2019, to encourage adoption of electric and hybrid vehicles. FAME-II scheme will offer an incentive of INR 150,000 each to 35,000 electric four-wheelers with an ex-factory price of up to INR 1,500,000 and incentive of INR 13,000 each to 20,000 strong hybrid four-wheelers with ex-factory price of up to INR 1,500,000.

11. Other supporting policies

Delhi Electric Vehicle Policy: Delhi EV Policy 2018 is notified by the Government of the National Capital Territory of Delhi. It will remain valid for 5 years from the date of notification. This is a new approach required to kick-start EV adoption in Delhi. The primary objective of the Delhi EV Policy 2018 is to improve Delhi's air quality by lowering emissions from automotive and

transportation sectors. Thus, this policy will seek to drive rapid adoption of BEVs. It is expected that these vehicles will contribute to 25 per cent of all new vehicle registrations by 2023.

National Electric Mobility Mission Plan: The National Electric Mobility Mission Plan (NEMMP), 2020 was introduced in India. The principal end objectives of the NEMMP are national energy security, mitigation of the adverse impact of vehicles on the environment and growth of domestic manufacturing capabilities. The NEMMP 2020, the mission document for the NEMM that was approved by the National Council for Electric Mobility on 29th August, 2012, sets the vision, lays the targets and provides the joint Government – industry vision for realizing the huge potential that exists for full range of efficient and environmentally friendly electric vehicle technologies by 2020. The NEMMP 2020 is a well researched document and relies on in-depth primary data based study conducted jointly by the Government and the industry which indicates that high latent demand for environmentally friendly electric vehicle technologies exists in the country. As per these projections, 6-7 million units of new vehicle sales of the full range of electric vehicles, along with resultant liquid fuel savings of 2.2 – 2.5 million tonnes can be achieved in 2020. This will also result in substantial lowering of vehicular emissions and decrease in carbon di-oxide emissions by 1.3 per cent to 1.5 per cent in 2020 as compared to a status quo scenario. However, in view of the significant barriers that exist today for these frontier technologies, the global experience indicates that this is an area where governments need to focus their efforts and provide support that is necessary for creation of the eco system and viable self-sustaining business in the near future. This includes providing initial impetus through demand support measures that facilitate faster consumer acceptance of these expensive newer technologies. In addition, government will also need to facilitate automotive R&D and put in place charging infrastructure. It is estimated that the government will need to provide support to the tune of Rs. 13000-14000 crore over the next 5-6 years. The industry will also need to match this with a much larger investment for developing the products and creating the manufacturing eco-system. NEMM is amongst the most

significant interventions of the government that promises to transform the automotive paradigm of the future by lessening the dependence on fossil fuels, increasing energy efficiency of vehicles and by providing the means to achieve ultimate objective of cleaner transportation that is compatible with sustainable renewable energy generation. This intervention will also help encourage the Indian automotive industry to shift to newer, cleaner technologies so that it builds its future competitive advantage around environmentally sustainable products, high end technologies, innovation and knowledge.

12. Conclusion

Increasing pollution and threat of global warming have accentuated the need to replace petroleum-fueled vehicles with emission-free substitutes. After decades of R&D, the industry has found EVs to be the best suitable substitute for traditionally fueled vehicles, which has resulted in the emergence of electric vehicles. However, in view of the significant barriers that exist today for these frontier technologies, the global experience indicates that this is an area where governments need to focus their efforts and provide support that is necessary for creation of the eco system and viable self-sustaining business in the near future. This includes providing initial impetus through demand support measures that facilitate faster consumer acceptance of these expensive newer technologies. In addition, government will also need to facilitate automotive R&D and put in place charging infrastructure.

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